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BEHAVIOURAL DISPOSITION AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' IN IBADAN METROPOLIS

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Abstract

The rate of indiscipline in schools in present day contemporary times is quite alarming and has made students consistently exhibit inappropriate behaviours such as bullying, fighting, truancy, disrespect, aggression and varied anti-social behaviours that are detrimental to their wellbeing, functioning and educational progression.

Indiscipline secondary school students might be at academic risk of dropping out of school. Studies have revealed that highly indiscipline students' are poorly motivated students with low academic self-efficacy and learned helplessness. These have some implications on their intellectual and developmental well-being. Though, studies have been carried out on the impact of indiscipline and achievement motivation on students. However, there is dearth of studies on impact of counseling on the behaviour disposition of students. Therefore, this study investigated guidance and counselling services as predictors of disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis, with specific focus on counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students and the consequence on their expressed discipline behaviour. The study adopted a descriptive research survey design of ex-post facto type. The population for this study consisted of all the secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis. Four hundred students were purposively selected from ten randomly selected secondary schools in Ibadan Metropolis. Guidance and Counselling Service Enhancing Student Discipline Scale (GCSESDS) which is a selfconstructed instrument by the researcher was used for data collection. Data was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression Analysis statistical tools at 0.05 level of significance. The result indicates that significant relationship exist between the independent variables and the dependent variable (disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students) in order of magnitude as thus:, counselling service ($R=0.342$, $p<0.05$), information service ($R=0.283$, $p<0.05$) and orientation service ($R=0.237$, $p<0.05$). The independent variables has significant joint impact of 25.59% on dependent variable $F(4/395) = 25.59$; $p<0.05$. Counselling had the highest relative impact ($\beta=0.396$) followed by information ($\beta=0.310$) and then orientation ($\beta=0.281$) made the least contribution. Counselling service, $r(398) = 0.342$, $p<.05$; information service, $r(398) = 0.283$, $p<.05$ and orientation service $r(398) = 0.237$, $p<.05$ correlates significantly with disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students. Therefore, government and concern agencies should give necessary and adequate funding and support to guidance and counselling activities in schools as a means to help foster discipline in schools and support students to discover their potentials and maximize them productively.

KeyWords: Counselling Service, Discipline, Guidance, Information Service, Orientation Service, School, and Students.

Introduction

The rate of indiscipline in schools in present day contemporary times is quite alarming and has made students consistently exhibit inappropriate behaviours such as bullying, fighting, truancy, disrespect, aggression and varied anti-social behaviours that are detrimental to their wellbeing, functioning and educational progression. However, discipline is characteristically considered to have significant positive impact on students' behavioural dispositions in and outside the classroom environment. This is often made possible when students are well guided and counselled to develop and attain the right values, virtues and dispositions that will enable them behave in the best appropriate manner. Utilizing guidance and counselling services provided by professionally trained and qualified School Guidance Counsellor that helps modify students' maladaptive behaviours to positively adaptive ones often serves as a golden opportunity for students to reflect and learn about the consequences of inappropriate behavioural dispositions, instill good shared values, and encourage the development of behaviours that are acceptable in school and classroom.

Students discipline in school is an essential part of their moral and intellectual development, the quality of education they attain that would help shape their future and life space. Guidance counsellors are crucial facilitators of behaviour modification process in schools, and they play a significant role in ensuring that students are well behaved, disciplined and that they receive worthwhile education that would add value to their lives. This indicates that the provision of guidance and counselling services to students are critical components of an ideal educational school system. This is because one of the key purposes of providing guidance and counselling services to students in schools is to help them develop their self-awareness and self-confidence. These are essential qualities that would enable students to appropriately take responsibility of their actions in life, make dynamic decisions and live a disciplined life. However, students who lack these qualities are inclined to exhibit disruptive behaviour, express indiscipline acts in the classroom and tend to struggle with their studies (Darakhshan & Shameem, 2023).

Sahu (2020) posits that guidance and counselling services provided for students in school is pivotal for their all-round developmental wellbeing as it helps foster quality growth and the building of sound personality in children. Through the provision of guidance and counselling services, children are helped to develop the capacity required to manage emotional challenges and effectively control socio-personal problems that could negatively impair their

developmental progress. Sahu (2020) further contended that ideal guidance and counselling services will help students integrate valuable experience in their day-to-day life.

Some experience could see students developing problem solving skills that will enable them have the ability to handle psycho-emotional problems that can impact negatively on their ability to concentrate on their studies in school. Invariably, this helps to positively shape behavioural dispositions of students and instill desired discipline in them.

Students that are well counselled and guided by school counsellors do learn how to appreciate self and others in a peaceful manner and equally live in harmony with others within and outside the school community. It aids to facilitate peaceful relationship between school administration and the students since proper counselling allows students to have the willpower to freely discuss with their teachers about diverse experiences that are unpleasant to them. Through this, they can easily share certain problems they might find difficult to share with their parents at home. For example, issues related to unemployment, sexual abuse, depression, drug abuse, alcohol abuse, fear of failing in exam, personal-social feelings, peer pressure to be involved in indiscipline acts, career challenges, etc, that can make them feel troubled and express anti-social behaviour towards self and others (Sahu, 2020).

According to Darakhshan and Shameem (2023) when counsellors render effective guidance and counselling services in school, it helps to foster creative collaboration between counsellors, parents, teachers, administrative personnel and significant others in school and it promotes a supportive, innovative and disciplined learning environment for students. This creative collaboration often help to identify and address issues of students indiscipline and maladaptive behaviours early, leading to improved personal and academic development. This shows that the provision of guidance and counselling services in schools is critical to students learning, behavioural conduct and discipline.

Guidance Counsellors provide varied guidance and counselling services for students in schools that help them adjust favourably and express disciplined behavioural dispositions in their daily conduct. For example, services such as: information, remedial, evaluation, orientation, counseling, individual inventory, placement, research and follow-up services are rendered to students to support their all-round positive development. However, the focus of this research study is on investigating guidance and counselling services as predictors of disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis, with specific attention on counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students.

Yusoff and Abdullah (2021) research determined the effect of counselling in enhancing discipline among secondary school students in Malaysia and found that the effective use of non-directive and directive counselling strategies helped indiscipline students to rediscover the danger associated with indiscipline and the need to adopt a positive discipline behavioural conduct and way of life. Vuleza (2021) affirmed that issues of indiscipline among students in Busia County in Kenya are on the increase in the like of drug abuse, truancy, bullying, theft, fighting, etc. Okirigwe (2020) study examined the influence of counselling services on students' discipline and academic adjustments in secondary schools in Rivers State and found that Counselling Services has positive influence on students' obedience to rules and regulation, of the school social environment, adaptation to physical school environment and the motivation to learn. Ngole (2022) stated that the use of counselling services helps enhance discipline and deliver social-psychological support to students in Tanzanian schools and despite years of the provision of counselling services, some schools are still experiencing issues of indiscipline such as; trancies, sexual and drug abuse, truancy, sexual molestation and dropouts from school.

Mogbana, et al (2022) found that information service provided by consellers in school to students help improve discipline, creative students' teachers' engagement and enhance competent interpersonal relationship. Thus, information services ensure positive development of students and makes teaching and learning take place in a conducive environment. It is in recognition of this development that information services that can stimulate students' consciousness of the need to be discipline and facilitate effective teaching and learning experience in schools are given the needed attention by school counsellors and educational planners. Researchers Mogbana, et al (2022) and Oviogbodu (2015) affirmed that In the process of guidance and counselling interactive relationship, information given help students' development holistically and prevent development of anti-social behaviour. Thus, information services serves as an ideal therapy to foster discipline behaviour among school children as it helps them develop the capacity to solve their problems in an effective manner that will ensure their emotional stability and functional adaptability.

Oduh, et al (2020) study determined the relationship between counselling information service and level of students' indiscipline among public secondary schools in Delta state North Senatorial District using correlation design and the outcome of the study shows that information service provided through counselling help prevent the expression of indiscipline behaviour by students. Cheruiyot and Simatwa (2016) hypothesized that provision of

orientation counselling services positively enhanced students' disposition of good behavior and improved academic performance. Eremie and Jackson (2019) reported that orientation services offered to students in schools indeed improves students' behavioural conduct and academic performance positively. The outcome of Shehu et al. (2021) study revealed that 80% of the respondents affirmed that they became well behaved and discipline after they received counselling orientation service in school. Ribadu (2021) stated that 63 % of respondents in his study strongly agreed that orientation programme enhances discipline among students and equally improve their academic performance.

Also, Hamilton Wentworth District School Board Report (2021) revealed that orientation programme provided in schools help promote a positive relationship climate that supports student to attain high academic achievement, sound mental health, and general wellbeing. The orientation policy detail proactive approach that utilizes strategies to promote the building of social skills, interventions to reinforce good discipline behaviour and to change students' maladaptive behaviours to adaptive ones and progressive discipline. Furthermore, orientation programme ensures that student enjoys and experience caring, safe and bias free learning environment that is free from discrimination and harassment. Thus, orientation Programmes focuses on providing equity educational experience, prevention of bullying behaviour, building pro-social skills and building healthy relationships within a school. To the best of my knowledge, there is paucity of research on guidance and counselling services as predictors of disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis. Therefore, to fill this research gap, this study investigated guidance and counselling services as predictors of disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis, with specific focus on counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students and the consequence on their expressed discipline behaviour.

Statement of the Problem

Maintaining discipline in secondary schools in Nigeria has being a recurring challenge over the years and worst off, in contemporary time, secondary school students have often display negative deviant behaviours that are detrimental to their developmental wellbeing. The rapid spread associated with the use of Information Communication Technology (ICT) have witness the manifestation of behaviours such as bullying, cyber bullying, sexual abuse, indecent dressing, sagging, drug use and abuse, truancy, fighting, social harassment, examination

malpractice etc. These expressed behaviours show cases act of indiscipline that have critically impaired the academic performance and behavioural dispositions of students in secondary school negatively. Therefore, based on this context, this study investigated guidance and counselling services as predictors of disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis, with specific focus on counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students and the consequence on their expressed discipline behaviour.

Objective of the Study

This study is focused on using empirical measures to investigate guidance and counselling services as predictors of disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this empirical study is to investigate guidance and counselling services as predictors of disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis and to specifically:

1. Determine the predictive impact of counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students have on their expressed disciplined behavioural disposition in Ibadan Metropolis.
2. Find out the joint impact counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students have on their expressed disciplined behavioural disposition in Ibadan Metropolis.
3. Establish the relative impact that counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students have on their expressed disciplined behavioural disposition in Ibadan Metropolis

Research Questions

1. What associative impact does counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students have on their expressed disciplined behavioural disposition in Ibadan Metropolis?

2. What joint impact does counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students have on their expressed disciplined behavioural disposition in Ibadan Metropolis?
3. What relative impact does counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students have on their expressed disciplined behavioural disposition in Ibadan Metropolis?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between the provision of counselling service and expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis
2. There is no significant relationship between the provision of information service and expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis
3. There is no significant relationship between the provision of orientation service and expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis

Methodology

The descriptive research survey design of ex-post facto type was adopted for this study. This type of design is used to establish relationships with the researcher having no control of the variables of interest and because of this; the variables cannot be manipulated by the researcher.

Population

The population for this study consisted of four thousand and fifty (4050) senior secondary school students (SSSII) in Ibadan Metropolis (Oyo State Ministry of Education).

Sample and Sampling Procedure

Four hundred (400) students were purposively selected from ten randomly selected secondary schools in Ibadan Metropolis. The four hundred purposively selected secondary school students were those that have received guidance and counselling services from their school counsellors. Forty secondary school students were selected from each of the ten secondary schools and these amounted to four hundred in total.

Instrumentation

Guidance and Counselling Service Enhancing Student Discipline Scale (GCSESDS) is a researcher self-constructed instrument used for data collection. This instrument is divided into five sub-sections consisting of (A) the demographic personal data, section (B) Student discipline, with items such as: My experience with guidance and counselling service in school has made me to: Be focused in school; Attend classes regularly; stop being a truant; Obey school rules and regulations; Dress decently. Section (C) Counselling service, has items such as due to counselling I received in school, I know the importance of: obeying rules; not involving in examination malpractice; not bullying other students; dressing neat to school; respecting my teachers and peers Section (D) Information service, has items such as the information I receive in school has help me to: be aware of my strength and weaknesses; develop good study habit; be attentive in class; use the library very well; consult with my teachers; and Section (E) Orientation service has items such as: The orientation service I receive in school has helped me to: manage peer pressure; be confident of myself; have self-control; avoid bad gangs; participate actively in school activities. Sub-sections B, C, D, and E have five items each with a five-point Likert response pattern of: strongly agree, agree, not sure, disagree and strongly disagree. The instrument has a coefficient reliability of .82 gotten through a test-re-test method.

Procedure for Administration

The researcher obtained permission to conduct this research work from the principals of schools used. Also, the consent of the counsellors was sort to help in identifying students that have gone through guidance counselling experience and instruments administered on them. The students were instructed that their responses were for research purposes and the researcher will treat it confidentially. The administration of the instrument last for three months and thereafter they were collected back for analysis.

Data Analysis

Data was analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression Analysis statistical tools at 0.05 level of significance. Multiple regressions were used to find out the joint and relative contributions of the independent variables on students' discipline. Also, PPMC was used to determine if the level of relationship between the variables was statistically significant to warrant rejection or acceptance of the hypotheses

Results

The results of the findings are thus, presented in the tables below:

Research Questions answered in the study

Research Question One: What associative impact does counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students have on their expressed disciplined behavioural disposition in Ibadan Metropolis?

Table1: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix of Relationship between the

Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	1	2	3	4
Student Discipline	400	33.26	7.07	1.000			
Counselling Service	400	30.48	8.42	.342	1.000		
Information Service	400	27.37	6.86	.283	.420	1.000	
Orientation_Service	400	24.36	5.19	.237	.393	.405	1.000

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

variable

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 1 shows the zero order correlation, mean and standard deviation of the variables. The results on the table indicates that significant relationship exist between the independent variables and the dependent variable (student discipline) in order of magnitude as thus:, counselling service (R=0.342, p<0.05), information service (R=0.283, p<0.05) and orientation service (R=0.237, p<0.05). This indicates that guidance and counselling services such as counseling, information and orientation has positive relationship with student discipline. This implies that counselled, well informed and oriented students are well behaved, focused and disciplined in school.

Research Question Two: What joint impact does counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students have on their expressed disciplined behavioural disposition in Ibadan Metropolis?

Table 2: Joint impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable

R	0.412
R Square	0.169
Adjusted R Square	0.164

Std. Error of the Estimate 6.4619

ANOVA						
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	Remark
Regression	11022.94	4	2755.74	25.59	.000	sig
Residual	42530.73	395	107.67			
Total	53553.67					

Table 2 shows that the independent variables (counseling, information, orientation services) has significant joint impact of 25.59% on dependent variable (student disciplined behavioural disposition) $F(4/395) = 25.59; p < 0.05$.

Research Question Three: What relative impact does counselling, information and orientation counselling services offered to students have on their expressed disciplined behavioural disposition in Ibadan Metropolis?

Table 3: Relative impact of the independent variables on the dependent variables

Variable	Unstandardised Coefficient	Standardised Coefficient	Rank	t	p	Remark	
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
Constant	25.20	1.179	-	21.38	.000	sig	
Counselling Service	.749	.093	.396	1 st	9.62	.000	sig
Information Service	.587	.071	.310	2 nd	7.611	.000	sig
Orientation Service	.503	.067	.281	3 rd	5.880	.000	sig

Table 3 shows that counselling had the highest relative impact on students discipline ($\beta=0.396$) followed by information ($\beta=0.310$) and then orientation ($\beta=0.281$) made the least contribution. This indicates that these independent variables are vital in enhancing students discipline in school.

Research Hypotheses One: There is no significant relationship between the provision of counselling service and expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis

Table 4: PPMC summary table showing significant relationship between counselling and expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	R	Df	P
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Student Discipline	400	33.26	7.07	.342	398	sig
Counselling Service	400	30.48	8.42			

Table 4 reveals that counselling service significantly correlates with expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students, $r(398) = 0.342, p < .05$, the mean and standard deviation for counseling service was 30.48 and 8.42 respectively. With this result, the H_0 : is thus, rejected.

Research Hypotheses Two: There is no significant relationship between the provision of information service and expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis

Table 5: PPMC summary table showing significant relationship between information service and expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students

Variable	N	Mean	SD	R	Df	P
Student Discipline	400	33.26	7.07	.283	398	sig
Information Service	400	27.37	6.86			

Table 5 reveals that information service significantly correlates with expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students, $r(390) = 0.283, p < .05$. The mean and standard deviation for information service was 27.37 and 6.86 respectively. With this result, the H_0 : is thus, rejected.

Research Hypotheses Three: There is no significant relationship between the provision of orientation service and expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students in Ibadan Metropolis

Table 6: PPMC summary table showing significant relationship between orientation service and expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students

Variable	N	Mean	SD	R	Df	P
Student Discipline	400	33.26	7.07	.237	398	Sig
Orientation Service	400	24.36	5.19			

Table 6 shows that orientation service correlates significantly with expressed disciplined behavioural disposition of secondary school students, $r(398) = 0.237, p < .05$. The mean and

standard deviation for self-concept was 36.37 and 9.805 respectively. With this result, the H_0 is thus, rejected.

Discussion of findings of the Study

The findings of the first research question shows that significant relationship exist between the independent variables and the dependent variable (disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students) in order of magnitude as thus:, counselling service ($R=0.342$, $p<0.05$), information service ($R=0.283$, $p<0.05$) and orientation service ($R=0.237$, $p<0.05$). This indicates that guidance and counselling services such as counselling, information and orientation has positive relationship with expressed disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students. This implies that counselled, well informed and oriented students are well behaved, focused and disciplined in school. This indicates that the provision of guidance and counselling services to students are critical components of an ideal educational school system. This is because one of the key purposes of providing guidance and counselling services to students in schools is to help them develop their selfawareness and self-confidence. These are essential qualities that would enable students to appropriately take responsibility of their actions in life, make dynamic decisions and live a disciplined life. This is consistent with the assertions of Sahu (2020) that guidance and counselling services provided for students in school is pivotal for their all-round developmental wellbeing as it helps foster quality growth and the building of sound personality in children. Through the provision of guidance and counselling services, children are helped to develop the capacity required to manage emotional challenges and effectively control socio-personal problems that could negatively impair their developmental progress. Sahu (2020) further contended that ideal guidance and counselling services will help students integrate valuable experience in their day-to-day life. Some experience could see students developing problem solving skills that will enable them have the ability to handle psychoemotional problems that can impact negatively on their ability to concentrate on their studies in school. Invariably, this helps to positively shape behaviour of students and instill desired discipline in them.

The result of the second research question shows that the independent variables (counselling, information and orientation services) has significant joint impact of 25.59% on dependent variable (disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students) $F(4/395) = 25.59$; $p<0.05$. This implies that guidance and counselling services such as (counselling, information, and orientation services) when offered to secondary school students, has

significant positive predictive impact on their behavioural conduct, discipline and general developmental wellbeing. This corroborate the assertion of Sahu (2020) That students that are well counselled and guided by school counsellors do learn how to appreciate self and others in a peaceful manner and equally live in harmony with others within and outside the school community. It aids to facilitate peaceful relationship between school administration and the students since proper counselling allows students to have the willpower to freely discuss with their teachers about diverse experiences that are unpleasant to them. Through this, they can easily share certain problems they might find difficult to share with their parents at home. For example, issues related to unemployment, sexual abuse, depression, drug abuse, alcohol abuse, fear of failing in exam, personal-social feelings, peer pressure to be involved in indiscipline acts, career challenges, etc, that can make them feel troubled and express antisocial behaviour towards self and others (Sahu, 2020).

The findings of the third research question indicates that Counselling had the highest relative impact on students' discipline ($\beta=0.396$) followed by information ($\beta=0.310$) and then orientation ($\beta=0.281$) made the least contribution. This shows that counselling serves as an ideal mechanism that is used to positively modify students' behaviour. Guidance Counsellors provide varied guidance and counselling services for students in schools that help them adjust favourably and express disciplined behavioural dispositions in their daily conduct. According to Darakhshan and Shameem (2023) when counsellors render effective guidance and counselling services in school, it helps to foster creative collaboration between counsellors, parents, teachers, administrative personnel and significant others in school and it promotes a supportive, innovative and disciplined learning environment for students. This creative collaboration often help to identify and address issues of student's indiscipline and maladaptive behaviours early, leading to improved personal and academic development. This shows that the provision of guidance and counselling services in schools is critical to students learning, behavioural conduct and discipline.

The result of the first research hypotheses shows that counselling service significantly correlates with disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students, $r(398) = 0.342, p < .05$, the mean and standard deviation for counseling service was 30.48 and 8.42 respectively. This indicates that counselling service can be effectively used to help students develop the capacity to self-regulate their behavioural dispositions positively. This finding corroborates that of previous researchers. For example, Okirigwe (2020) found that counselling services has positive influence on students' obedience to rules and regulation, of the school.

Ngole (2022) reported that counselling was effectively used to manage and improve discipline among secondary school students.

The findings of the second research hypotheses revealed that information service significantly correlates with disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students, $r(398) = 0.283, p < .05$. The mean and standard deviation for information service was 27.37 and 6.86 respectively. This implies that information service can help students' appropriately appraised their strength and weaknesses and self-rediscover their potentials. For example, Mogbana, et al (2022) found that information service provided by consellers in school to students help improve discipline, creative students teachers engagement and enhance competent interpersonal relationship. Thus, information services ensures positive development of students and makes teaching and learning take place in a conducive environment. Researchers Mogbana, et al (2022) and Oviogbodu (2015), affirmed that in the process of guidance and counselling interactive relationship, information given help students' development holistically and prevent development of anti-social behaviour. Thus, information services serves as an ideal therapy to foster discipline behaviour among school children as it helps them develop the capacity to solve their problems in an effective manner that will ensure their emotional stability and functional adaptability.

The result of the third research hypotheses revealed that orientation service significantly predict disciplined behavioural disposition among secondary school students, $r(398) = 0.237, p < .05$. The mean and standard deviation for self-concept was 36.37 and 9.805 respectively.

This shows that orientation is vital for students' intellectual, behavioural and developmental adjustment for functionality and productivity. Also, Hamilton Wentworth District School Board Report (2021) revealed that orientation programme provided in schools help promote a positive relationship climate that supports student to attain high academic achievement, sound mental health, and general well-being. The orientation policy detail proactive approach that utilizes strategies to promote the building of social skills, interventions to reinforce good discipline behaviour and to change students' maladaptive behaviours to adaptive ones and progressive discipline. Likewise, Oduh et al (2020) study found that majority of the students agreed that the use of orientation programme help reduce the incidence of indiscipline among students and enhance the expression of disciplined good behaviour by students.

Recommendations

1. Students should be given adequate orientation, of the benefit of utilizing guidance and counselling services as a means for them to maximize their potentials. This would encourage them to go for counselling as the need arises.
2. The school authorities should give positive support to the activities of trained professional counsellors and provide them conducive environment and facilities to function in school.
3. The government and concern agencies should give necessary and adequate funding and support to guidance and counselling activities in schools as a means to help foster discipline in schools and support students to discover their potentials and maximize them productively.

Conclusion

The provision of guidance and counselling services such as counselling, information and orientation are crucial to facilitating needed behaviour modification process in schools, and they play a significant role in ensuring that students are well behaved, disciplined and that they receive worthwhile education that would add value to their lives.

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